

ON STATE PROPERTY IN THE ECONOMY (using the example of media coverage)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10199345>

Dmitriy Sorokin

doctoral researcher Academy of Public Administration
under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

***Abstract.** This article is devoted to issues of state ownership in some solutions to the management of state assets. Consideration of issues related to property rights and its significance plays an important role. The problems of maintaining state property include several points related to ineffective management, failures and incompetent organization of work.*

***Keywords:** state, assets, state property, economy, management of state property, control, accounting, monitoring*

At the present stage, the development of the economy and economic relations depend on the chosen promotion strategy and the measures taken to expand the opportunities for successful economic recovery. One of the important issues is the state form of ownership, which has become the dominant form in the state property system. Historically, various operations in the world economy carried out on state property (nationalization, limiting the number of private owners and attempts to eliminate private property) have not yielded any positive results [3].

The relevance of considering the problem of state property and its essence is based on the fact of the development of a market economy and, as a consequence, the manifestation of a variety of forms of ownership and reform of the state property management system. Therefore, consideration of issues related to property rights and its significance plays an important role. The problems of managing state property include several points, including bureaucratization of the management structure, failures and improper work in the field of property management, ineffective control over the activities of state-owned objects.

Any society has certain material benefits that constitute the national wealth of a particular state. In the process of developing the system of appropriation of material goods, certain types of property emerged. In a broad sense, there is the following definition of state property, in particular, state property is property, including means and products of production, owned by the state in full or on the basis of shared or joint ownership. State property may include any owned property necessary for the

performance of its functions, as well as shares of joint stock companies. The state may own shares in joint stock companies of various forms of ownership, in addition, the state may own any property necessary to carry out its functions.

State property is property owned by the Republic of Uzbekistan and property owned locally. State property as an economic category means that property belongs to the people represented by representative bodies of state power elected by them. From this point of view, the right of state property in an objective sense is a set of legal norms that, first of all, secure and protect the ownership of material goods by the people (the population belonging to a specific territory) represented by a representative body of state power elected by them, and also establishing the procedure for the acquisition, use and alienation of state property [2].

Particularly noted is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the protection of property rights. For example, by presidential decree, decisions on the allocation of property will be canceled only by the court, the liquidation of a legal entity will no longer be a basis for termination of rights to land, homeowners will be able to cancel permanent “registration” without the consent of non-relatives. On August 24, the President of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev signed the Decree “On measures to reliably protect the inviolability of property rights, prevent unjustified interference in property relations, and increase the level of capitalization of private property.” The document, effective September 1, 2022, abolishes a number of procedures and requirements providing for direct or indirect restrictions on the right to own, use and dispose of private property [1].

The types of state property should also be considered separately. The concept of ownership is very complex and implies not only two forms of ownership, but also the various types into which each form is divided. Such a variety of classifications arises as a result of the fact that subjects of law, although united within the same form, differ in the methods of regulating property with their participation. Another important issue is current trends in the management of state property. The basic principles of state property management in Uzbekistan define some goals for the effective development of state property:

- a) building the structure of state ownership in such a way as to provide the prerequisites for economic growth;
- b) involvement of the maximum number of state-owned objects in economic circulation;
- c) through effective management of state property, achieve an increase in the state budget;
- d) with the help of state assets, attract investment in the real sector;

e) increasing the level of financial and economic performance indicators of organizations.

There are several main ways to manage state property, depending on the object of management:

- first type - objects owned by the state on a full basis (as the sole owner). At the same time, the state has the right to carry out any actions regarding the property;

- the second type - objects that are partially owned by the state. The state manages such objects in accordance with the share of ownership of the property relative to other owners;

- third type - objects that do not fully belong to the state, but are dependent on the state on a different basis. In this case, the state does not have a direct influence on the property; it indirectly manages or, more correctly, regulates the functioning of the property.

As for state ownership in the economic sector of Uzbekistan, the trend of denationalization of property and its further commercialization is actively used. Property in the Republic of Uzbekistan is inviolable. Everyone has the right to property. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the existence of any forms of ownership is allowed that contribute to the effective functioning of the economy and the growth of people's well-being. The inviolability and equal conditions for the development of all forms of property are guaranteed by law. The Republic of Uzbekistan creates all the necessary conditions for the owner to ensure the safety and increase of his property. In this process, the principle of public law is replaced by private property rights, subject to the removal of some frameworks and restrictions aimed at protecting the enterprise from a competitive market, but the principle of restrictions on the use of property remains in effect.

As a result of studying the theoretical foundations of the state property system, methods of managing state property, as well as analyzing the results of managing state property over the past few years, a number of theoretical conclusions were identified on the effectiveness of state property management and recommendations were developed to increase the usefulness of state property in the country's economy.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Property Law. <https://lex.uz/acts/111455>
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for the effective organization of the activities of the agency for managing state assets”, dated March 24, 2023 No. PP-101
3. State property [Electronic resource] / Electronic dictionary. - Access mode

URL: <http://dic.academic.ru/> (Access date: 11/27/2015)

4. Bulanov B.S. State regulation of a market economy - M.: Publishing house RAGS, 2003. -832 p.
5. Сарбитова В. Уровни речи в корейском языке. Казань. 2018.